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SCIENTIFIC PRIORITIES FOR SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT OF URBANIZED AREAS IN THE DIGITAL AGE

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Annotation: The implementation of high-tech technologies of the Internet of things is a necessary condition for achieving sustainable development of urban areas. Improving the urban ecosystems functioning quality necessitates the development and implementation of scientific priorities for the sustainable development of urban areas. A decision support system has been developed for choosing scientific directions, which ensures the implementation of the main functions of scientific and technological development and the ability to compare the results of management efficiency in the Internet of things. The system includes predictive mathematical models of urban areas scientific and technological development and algorithms for monitoring the effectiveness of the Internet of things, depending on the formulation of scientific problems and the object of study.

Keywords: efficiency, internet of things, knowledge-intensive solutions, infrastructure, ecosystem, urbanized area, environment

Solving the problems of energy saving of the Internet of things (IoT) requires effective methods at all levels of urban areas management. Considerable attention is paid to the accounting and control of the Internet of things energy resources consumption at modern enterprises, therefore, the issues of building systems for monitoring technological processes and accounting for energy consumption in various areas of management do not lose their relevance [1, 2].

In general, managing the Internet of things is a system of monitoring and control measures to assess the state of the object of study, analyze ongoing

processes and timely identify trends in its change [3, 4]. Nevertheless, monitoring the effectiveness of the Internet of Things of any production system should provide a determination of its state and the efficiency of the organization of the technological process, create prerequisites for improving and improving the quality of the functioning of the system and its components, and become the basis for the development and implementation of scientific priorities for sustainable development. That is, the system for monitoring the energy efficiency of the Internet of things should be built not only as a technical system for accounting and controlling energy consumption, but also as a system that provides the managerial aspect of the efficiency improvement process [5, 6].

It is relevant to create a system for collecting, analyzing and using data on the final consumption of energy resources of the Internet of things to form a comparative base for the efficiency of using energy resources in urban areas. At the same time, when developing energy monitoring systems and methods for implementing its functions, it is important to take into account the individual characteristics of the object of study (the nature of the enterprise production activity, the features of the technological processes organization, the operating modes of structural elements). It is necessary to develop a system for monitoring the effectiveness of the resource intensity of the Internet of things, which would ensure the implementation of the main monitoring functions and the ability to compare the results of the resource intensity of urbanized territories, take into account the specifics of the study object and contribute to the adoption of effective management decisions on the scientific areas implementation.

Monitoring the effectiveness of the Internet of things involves increasing the level of efficiency in the use of external and internal resources, resulting in a change in the quality of the state and functioning of the production system of urbanized territories, determining the possibilities for introducing energy-saving measures and high technologies, achieving the planned tasks of saving electricity, minimizing the negative consequences of urbanization.

This is a set of measures aimed at the implementation of the main functions: observation, assessment of the object state, forecasting and control, specified by the specifics of the study object and the tasks set. Control systems and determine additional requirements for the way monitoring is performed, as well as the IoT performance metrics to be monitored.

To ensure the implementation of the main functions of energy monitoring of the Internet of things (observation, assessment of the state of an object, forecasting and control), it is necessary to develop appropriate approaches and methods that would allow taking into account the conditions of the initial state and the features of the functioning of the system of scientific and technical development of urbanized territories and its objects; indicators of technical, technological, energy efficiency that affect the power consumption of the Internet

of things; provided an opportunity to identify sources of irrational energy costs and negative trends, and also contributed to the adoption of effective decisions on the implementation of scientific directions for the development of the entire system and structural elements.

However, depending on the level of the hierarchy of the urban areas scientific and technological development problem, the implementation of monitoring the effectiveness of the Internet of things requires the consistent implementation of certain actions. Since monitoring is one of the necessary ways to increase the level of efficiency of the Internet of things of the entire enterprise and its structural elements, this activity should be carried out on an ongoing basis, taking into account the fact that the information obtained as a result of monitoring affects the adoption of the correct management decision, and therefore overall result. Moreover, the main principle of the functioning of the system for monitoring the effectiveness of the Internet of things should be the continuity (cyclicality) of organizing object-by-object control and accounting for the information received to further improve the process of implementing scientific priorities and planning modes for efficient energy consumption of the Internet of things. The implementation of each of the functions of energy monitoring of the Internet of Things is a complex task that requires a thorough study of the system functioning features and its structural elements, the formation of a set of Internet of Things performance indicators for each specific case, the construction of predictive mathematical models of scientific and technological development of urban areas and the development of control algorithms efficiency of energy consumption depending on the formulation of scientific problems and the study object.

When monitoring, there is a need to obtain scientific information representative of various objects in urban areas. Therefore, in accordance with the hierarchical structure, the limits of monitoring should be determined: unit, structural element, technological process, hierarchical level, production, enterprise. One of the important steps in creating a system for monitoring the effectiveness of the resource intensity of the Internet of things is the formation of a set of performance indicators for each level of the urbanized territories hierarchy, taking into account the structuring of goals for the research problem chosen statement.

The distribution of quantitative and qualitative indicators of the effectiveness of the Internet of Things by the levels of the management hierarchy has been carried out, which makes it possible to quickly obtain the necessary information for making management decisions.

At the enterprise level, a set of indicators of the effectiveness of the Internet of things is sufficient, reflecting the general trend in the resource intensity efficiency, which does not require detailed consideration of the characteristics of the lower levels [7, 8]. The existing set of indicators should reflect the change in the level of efficiency of the Internet of things as a result of the implementation of

measures and projects to improve efficiency [9, 10]. An integral part of solving not only the issue of energy saving of the Internet of things, but also obtaining the necessary information about the object of study is the energy audit of the enterprise, which (in addition to identifying sources of irrational energy costs and developing energy saving measures) makes it possible to determine a number of indicators that are not taken into account by the means existing at the enterprise accounting for energy resources, but characterize the scientific and technical state of the object and the efficiency of its functioning [11, 12].

There are many approaches to assessing the effectiveness of the resource intensity of the Internet of Things, based on the regulation of energy costs, the determination of unit costs, and the use of energy balances [13, 14]. However, there are no comprehensive indicators of the effectiveness of the Internet of things, which made it possible to compare various directions for the implementation of high-tech technological solutions, both in terms of external parameters of sustainable development of urbanized territories, and in terms of internal ones (indicators of resource intensity, methods for managing the operating mode and power consumption mode).

The development of methods for assessing the Internet of things efficiency level has been carried out, which provide the ability to comprehensively take into account all aspects of the scientific and technical problem of studying the effectiveness of sustainable development objects in urban areas and help identify the causes of inefficient implementation of scientific priorities, shortcomings in the organization of the scientific and technological process and managing the operating mode of the selected research object.

Scientific and technical analysis involves comparing objects of the same hierarchical level within urbanized areas, as well as comparing similar objects in other urbanized areas. Moreover, the assessment of the level of efficiency of the Internet of things is carried out taking into account the best internal scientific indicators, the best indicators of other enterprises, and average indicators in the digital industry. The decision support system implements the definition of the goal of scientific and technical analysis, which will determine all further decisions, starting with the choice of scientific indicators and objects for comparison and ending with the method of presenting data and the structure of priorities, areas and sub-areas of research, performance indicators for each area (sub-areas) urbanized territories digital economy.

The implemented decision support system involves a thorough study and construction of links between all components of the problem of the effectiveness of the Internet of things, depending on the formulation and hierarchical level at which the study is carried out, a clear display of the links between goals (subgoals) and indicators of scientific and technological development of urbanized territories. The decision support system provides:

- systematic comparative analysis of urbanized territories sustainable development scientific indicators, objects and trends in their change;
- determination of the Internet of Things efficiency level in urban areas;
- identifying the causes of inefficient implementation of scientific priorities and ways to eliminate them;
- analysis of the urbanized territories sustainable development level dynamics as a reflection of the effectiveness of management actions to improve the efficiency of using the Internet of things.

The results of a comparative analysis contribute to the identification of scientific and technical problems in efficiency compared to other science-intensive solutions for the sustainable development of urban areas [15, 16]. One of the ways to assess the level of efficiency of the Internet of Things for a group of objects of the same type is to determine the rating of an object based on a multivariate comparison [17, 18]. Such an assessment provides for taking into account the existing set of indicators of the effectiveness of the Internet of things and allows to identify the best (worse) in terms of the efficiency of using objects of the Internet of things that are of practical importance for deciding on the implementing scientific and technical solutions priority.

The next step is to determine the scale and nature of the scientific and technical problem in order to identify the reasons for the difference in the efficiency of the Internet of things and ways to improve it to ensure the sustainable development of urban areas. This requires analysis and understanding of the measures by which the best objects have succeeded. For these purposes, methods for assessing the level of efficiency of the Internet of things based on methods for the multi-criteria classification of possible states of an object according to individual classification characteristics of efficiency have been implemented. Determination of belonging of the study object to one of the classes, ordered by the level of efficiency, not only ensures the determination of its actual level, but helps to identify shortcomings in the organization of the scientific and technical process of sustainable development of urban areas. The scientific information collected in the monitoring process should become the basis for further increasing the level of efficiency and be used for effective scientific and technical planning at the enterprise, as well as monitoring the resource intensity and effectiveness of decisions made to increase the level of sustainable development of urban areas.

Management systems of urbanized territories necessarily contain subsystems for operational management of the efficiency of the resource intensity of the Internet of things [19, 20]. The basis for building such a system is to identify the dependence of the volume of energy consumption of the Internet of things at any facility on the values of a number of production and technological parameters (indicators) that have an important impact, in comparison with which the effectiveness of management decisions is determined.

The implemented predictive mathematical models of the scientific and technological development of urbanized territories represent some of the most realistic forecasts of the level of energy consumption of the Internet of Things that is necessary and possible to achieve at a given facility. This is a certain rate of absolute resource consumption, which is not ideal, that is, the minimum necessary for a given object, but quite well reflects the level of efficiency of the resource intensity of the Internet of things actually achieved at the object of study.

The development of mathematical models of scientific and technical development of urbanized territories has been implemented for:

- the study object, taking into account its actual operating conditions in order to monitor the effectiveness of the Internet of things;
- a similar object, which is preferable in terms of efficiency in a group of the same type, for the purpose of comparative analysis.

Moreover, as the energy consumption standards of the Internet of Things, it is possible to use the limits of the confidence intervals built for them, which makes it possible to take into account the random nature of the Internet of Things power consumption processes and the residual error of their modeling.

Monitoring can be considered as an analysis of the chronology of the use of resources in urban areas over a certain period of time and forecasting their consumption. To determine the expected energy consumption, it is necessary to use an appropriate approach that allows leveling the influence of random factors and providing the possibility of comparing monitoring data of urban areas. The main criterion that determines the efficiency of the system of urbanized territories and its structural subdivisions is to provide the consumer with system resources in an amount equal to his needs. The consumption of resources in urban areas is characterized by unevenness and is formed under the influence of many, often uncontrollable factors. The incompleteness and improbability of the initial information leads to planning errors.

Changes in the time of resource consumption in urban areas are random processes, that is, randomly dependent on time, internal and external factors. Consumption of resources in urban areas is a variable process, and the dominant factors are the time of day and social factors.

The power consumption of the Internet of things is determined by the amount of information passing through the elements of the system, as well as by certain technological factors, the impact of which can be adjusted by optimizing the operating mode. When building a model of power consumption, it is important to take into account the model of the external environment, which is a model of a random process of information transfer.

Therefore, forecasting the resources consumption in urban areas is the first step in solving the problem of planning the operating mode and controlling the power consumption of the Internet of things in order to improve the efficiency of

ecosystems. At the same time, in order to obtain a qualitative forecast, it is necessary to ensure the most complete consideration of the dominant factors. This will allow to control the flow of the process and influence the factors that cause irrational consumption of energy resources of the Internet of things.

The implementation of the forecasting function when building a system for monitoring the effectiveness of the Internet of things for the sustainable development of urban areas should include two stages: the formation of standard resource supply schedules; building models of resource consumption, taking into account standard schedules, as well as scientific and technical factors that affect the Internet of things power consumption efficiency level.

The Internet of things energy consumption volumes at any technological facility are random values, since in the general case they depend on a large number of technical, technological, organizational and climatic factors.

A systematic analysis of the energy efficiency of the Internet of things requires a continuous-flow analysis of the dynamics of scientific and technical indicators and the identification of trends towards deterioration in efficiency. The control system should provide not only regular recording of the energy consumption of the Internet of things and its fluctuations, which can and should be localized, but also the ability to identify, based on the analysis of performance indicators, certain energy aspects and processes that need to be improved.

The control system is designed to provide an assessment of the energy management of the Internet of Things, identify errors in the organization of the operation mode of objects and sections of the production process that require improvement, taking into account the best scientific and technical examples of efficient use. Thus, the system for monitoring the effectiveness of the Internet of things contains:

1. A subsystem for operational control of the effectiveness of the Internet of things, which provides for: current control of the dynamics of scientific and technical solutions as the dominant factor that determines the construction of an effective power consumption mode for the Internet of things; current monitoring of the dynamics of the performance indicators of the Internet of things from the standpoint of their compliance with certain ranges in terms of the level of efficiency of the Internet of things; control of compliance with the basic energy consumption of the Internet of things.

2. A subsystem for comparative analysis of the effectiveness of the Internet of things, including procedures: comparing the Internet of things performance indicators dynamics with similar indicators of the best objects in terms of efficiency from the group of the same type; analysis of the compliance with the actual mode of power consumption of the best in terms of efficiency objects of the Internet of Things from the group of the same type.

The process of monitoring the implementation of energy consumption standards for the Internet of things and the dynamics of performance indicators should be based on the use of probabilistic-statistical algorithms. The implemented algorithms for monitoring the effectiveness of the resource intensity of the Internet of things is a procedure for sequentially identifying changes in the properties of a time series when it is considered over a certain period of time, which allows to determine the moments of a non-random decrease in the efficiency of the resource intensity of the Internet of things. It is expedient to control the fulfillment of the established standards of energy consumption in operational efficiency control systems by registering the number of cases where the actual values of the energy consumption of the Internet of Things go beyond the confidence interval, through which the appropriate standard for the sustainable development of urban areas is established.

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